

Pseudomonas fluorescens from the rhizospheres of rice, citrus, cotton, peanut, and other crops that reduced ShR.

In in vitro assays, *P. fluorescens* isolated from citrus restricted *S. oryzae* growth. In the greenhouse, treating *S. oryzae*-inoculated rice plants with *P. fluorescens* restricted development of ShR lesions.

In a field experiment, replicated plots were planted with IR20 and IET1444 seedlings with and without *P. fluorescens* treatment. The treated plants also were sprayed with 10^8 cfu/ml *P. fluorescens* at early and late booting. At booting, the middle of the uppermost flag leaf of all plants was inoculated with *S. oryzae* using the standard grain

inoculum technique. ShR incidence was recorded from 100 randomly selected tillers per plot. At harvest, number of grains per tiller and infected grains per tiller, 1,000-grain weight, and yield per plot were recorded (see table). Treatment with *P. fluorescens* substantially reduced ShR seventy and increased grain yield. *S*

Controlling bakanae (Bak) and foot rot disease with fungicide seed treatments

B. B. Sarkar, Plant Protection Research Wing, State Agricultural Research Station, Arundhutinagar 799003, Tripura, India

We tested eight fungicide seed dressings for controlling Bak and foot rot disease

(*Gibberella fujikuroi* (Saw.) Wr. = *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheldon) on IET1444 in 1984 kharif.

Seed was collected from a field severely infected with Bak and foot rot disease. All fungicides except carbendazim were thoroughly mixed with dry seed at 5 g/kg seed. Carbendazim was mixed at 2 g/kg seed.

An untreated control was maintained. Sprouted seeds were sown in seedbeds and transplanted into the main field 21 d later. Disease incidence was recorded 20 d after sowing and 35 d after transplanting.

Average disease intensity and yield (see figure) showed that all fungicide treatments significantly reduced disease incidence, although none gave complete control. Carbendazim performed best, followed by PCNB and Agrosan GN. *S*

Diseased plants (no./1000)

Efficacy of seed treatments for controlling bakanae and foot rot disease, Tripura, India.

Correlation between green leafhopper (GLH) incidence and tungro (RTV)

R. Saroja, M. Suriachandraselvan, and N. Raju, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Tirur 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

In 1984-85 sornavari (Apr-May to Aug-Sep), RTV destroyed 28,000 ha of rice in Chingleput District. Experiments and

Correlation between GLH occurrence and RTV incidence, 1984-85, Tirur, India.

Month	GLH density		RTV (%)
	Light trap catch (no.)	GLH/hill	
Apr	428	0	0
May	586	0	0
Jun	926	11	8
Jul	181,196	90	93
Aug	30,343	17	35
Sep	2,407	11	21
Oct	906	10	10
Nov	1,278	5	0
Dec	10,221	5	0
Jan	8,130	3	5
Feb	926	4	3
Mar	418	5	0